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Title

Reflexivity, responsibilities, and self: analyzing the legal transition from double to single parenthood and suggesting changes in policy

Abstract

Institutional Ethnography (IE) is a feminist research approach (Smith, 1987, 1990, 2005, 2006) that allows analyzing how texts organize the everyday life of people and the institutional processes and discourses that characterize that social organization (Manicom and Campbell 1995).

This paper is based on a two-year IE on the legal transition from double to single parenting in four European countries (Tartari, 2019). The study analyses texts, processes, and discourses that organize the courts' evaluations on children's custody and the strategies of professionals and lone mothers. The research begins from the standpoint of the lone mothers and investigates through in-depth interviews how the legal institutions and professionals shape mothers' phase of transition from double to single parenting (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). Then, the research involves legal professionals and asks them – through a particular kind of in-depth interview, the interview to the double – for explaining how they read and interpret the legal texts translating them in a language that fits the needs of their clients, that is the mothers. The analysis allows illustrating how texts'

interpretations, translations, and discourses shape the everyday life of mothers and their selves during that legal transition.

This paper draws on the reflexive practices (Hesse-Biber and Piatelli 2014; DeVault 1990) of both the participants and the researcher. This paper is organized into a review of the literature that frames the reflexive practices of the research, an introduction to the overall research study, a discussion that focuses on the three main actors of this research study and process: the researcher, the women and the professionals involved as participants. For each of them, the paper presents the methodology used to develop reflexivity and responsible practices for social change, the process of interrogating the self and the selves in the process of negotiating positionality. The conclusions offer some reflections on how to conjugate reflexivity with responsibility in practice during the research process.

Notes on the research project

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Lone mothers, gender, power relations, Institutional Ethnography, intersectionality

Introduction

This paper aims to contribute to the academic discussion on how to develop reflexive practices (Hesse-Biber and Piatelli 2012; Reid 2018) in Institutional Ethnography (Smith, 1987, 1990, 2005, 2006; Manicom and Campbell 1995) for both the participants and the researchers.

The paper draws on a two-year Institutional Ethnography that explores the legal transition from double to single mothering in four European countries (Tartari, 2019). The study analyses texts, processes, and discourses that organize the courts' evaluations on children's custody and the strategies of professionals and lone mothers during this transition.

The study is funded by the European Union, through an individual grant provided by the MSC Actions organized by the European Commission. Therefore the commissioning body is a public body with different power relations in comparison to the national governments' legislation (e.g., EU has not legislative-executive competence about the law for children custody), but with the capacity to orient public policy and propose legislation to the EU member states.

The main goal of my Institutional Ethnography project is social change. Therefore, I chose Institutional Ethnography for its ability to valorize the women's standpoint in the research process and to problematize the social relations and organization that lie under the experience of women in their everyday life. To enhance reflexivity and to question power imbalance during the research process, I utilized insights and practices from feminist researchers (Collins, 1998, 2000; Harding, 1991, 1993; Smith, 1987). I considered reflexivity as a "holistic process that takes place along all stages of the research process". (Hesse-Biber & Piatelli 2012, 6).

This paper is organized into a presentation of the literature that frames the reflexive practices of my research, an introduction to the overall research study, a discussion that focuses on the three main actors of this research study and process: the researcher, the women involved as participants, the professionals involved as participants. For each of them, I will present the methodology I used to develop reflexivity and responsible practices for social change, and I will draw on the process of

interrogating the self and the selves in the process of negotiating positionality (e.g., Naples 1996; Collins 1998). Finally, I conclude with some reflections on how to conjugate reflexivity with responsibility in practice during the research process.

Analyzing these reflexive processes and practices has the aim to not neglect the participation of women as citizens in the process of social change in the EU context and the researcher's power and privilege in conducting and ensuring this participation in a responsible way. Discussing these aspects concerns not only an academic audience, but also a non-academic audience like policy-makers, stakeholders, and activists who are often the final recipients of research results.

Insights from the literature

In this paper, I am interested in deepening some specific aspects of reflexivity in doing research with and for women empowerment and social justice. The complexity of my study, with Institutional Ethnography fieldwork in four different countries, raises questions about how to act reflexively in different countries with women who belong to different cultures and live in different social contexts. As my interest concerns using reflexive practices for the entire research process, my analysis is based on the literature that concerns the following topics: the feminist contributions to holistic reflexive methodologies, reflexivity as a self-critical action during the overall research process, how to develop reflexivity in research participants, how to bring alternative forms of knowledge into the public discourse in a responsible way.

First, the *feminist contributions to reflexive methodologies* concern, in the first instance, how we know what we know and the role of the self in knowing what we know (Collins, 1998, 2000; Harding, 1991, 1993; Smith, 1987). In other words, the knowledge of the world is mediated by the self, experiences, and biography of the researcher and each participant, and "all knowledge is affected by the social conditions under which it is produced and that it is grounded in both the social location and the social biography of the observer and the observed" (Mann & Kelley, 1997, p. 392). Such feminist epistemology assumes that the world is socially constructed, consists of multiple

perspectives and realities, and researchers can explore it while considering, with a critical gaze, different perspectives or “positions” from which the world can be experienced. The “knower” can be considered as an expert who is engaged in an unbalanced relationship of power with the known (Oakley, 1998). Therefore, the main reflection should concern how to mend such imbalance through discourses and practices in the research field. Furthermore, in Institutional Ethnography research reflexivity concerns also how to manage and avoid institutional capture (Smith, 2005) and privileged irresponsibility (Tronto, 1993).

Second, feminist research considers *reflexivity as a self-critical action that takes place during the overall research process* (Hertz, 1996). From the writing of the research proposal until the publication of the results and their presentation to an audience, self-criticism can help the researchers in discussing their positions toward participants and research topics, in building a fruitful relationship of trust with the participants, and pursuing social justice. Researchers should reflect on the issue that reliable objectivity could be achieved not by neglecting the role of the self in the process of knowledge, but by considering its different locations and positions.

In such a perspective, the researcher should be critically self-reflexive about personal and cultural biases in the process of knowing the world (Schutz 1964) and should interrogate her positionality and her multiple selves as an outsider, insider, or both. Feminist research highlight that the *borderline* position is the most fruitful in terms of research knowledge. Naples (1996, 2003) argues that the researcher can be an *insider* in one time and place and an *outsider* in another one, with the need to reconcile these different selves and to recognize that these different positions can have different degrees of *insiderness* and *outsiderness*. This brings to the consideration that the researcher can access multiple standpoints, negotiate them, recognize the existence of multiple subjectivities and the need to conduct a “border work” (Anzaldúa, 1987; Parameswaran, 2001; Patai & Gluck, 1991; Spivak, 1988; Trinh, 1991). About this specific topic, literature on Institutional Ethnography still lacks contributions on comparative and multi-countries studies.

Third, reflexivity does not concern only the researcher, but also the research participants. Therefore, the researcher should interrogate herself about *how to develop reflexivity in research participants*, because it is just with the use of this approach that research can bring alternative forms of knowledge into public discourse (Hesse-Biber & Piatelli, p. 6). Mainly, the aim is to negotiate power and co-construct knowledge with participants. We have at our disposal different practices to develop reflexivity in and with research participants in Institutional Ethnography. Researchers can utilize the strategy of recognizing similarities and differences between the researcher and participants (Edwards 1990; Anderson 1998). Then, the researcher should engage herself in dialogical conversations with the participants. For instance, Anderson (1998) engaged herself in these dialogical practices and relationships and was able to exchange and co-construct knowledge through the revelation of her biography, experiences, and opinions. In addition, researchers can organize specific activities to stimulate and bring to the light participants' reflexivity or to engage them as reflexive co-researchers, like PAR (Lykes & Hershberg 2012; Lykes 1997) or specific forms of focus groups, like interpretive focus groups (Dodson and Schmalzbauer 2005), or 'The Listening Guide' (Mauthner and Doucet, 1998) and the 'I' poems (Reid 2018).

Fourth, trying to *bring alternative forms of knowledge into the public discourse in a responsible way* implies working on ethical and strategic aspects. Encouraging participants' reflexivity can help in reaching new understandings and unveiling counter-hegemonic narratives to bring into the public discourse. However, ethical aspects should be considered in exposing participants' experiences and voices to different audiences. About these topics, significant contributions come from public ethnography practices (e.g., Vannini 2018) and the experience of feminist researchers. How to reach audiences to share new understandings and narratives and the participants' degrees of involvement and visibility of their bodies and voices should be discussed reflexively at different points of the research process (from the consent form until the selection of fragments to bring to the public audience). About this specific topic, Institutional Ethnography literature still lacks contributions.

The research study. Aims and methods

The title of my project – STRESS-Mums – reflects the interest and the aim of pointing out the standpoints and experience of lone mothers who are the main research participants of this study.

The study is conducted in four European countries (Italy, Spain, Belgium, and the UK), selected on the basis of specific criteria concerning the legislation on children's custody and socio-cultural characteristics. The main goal is exploring the legal transition from double to single parenthood due to separation or divorce from the standpoint of single mothers using the approach of Institutional Ethnography (Smith 2005; 2006). In particular, the study aims to analyze how texts' interpretations, translations, and discourses shape the everyday life of mothers and their selves during that legal transition.

The research begins by analyzing the standpoint of the lone mothers through in-depth interviews, which investigate how the legal institutions and professionals shape this phase of transition from double to single parenting and the disjunctures between the women's actual life and needs and the institutions' practices and discourses. In-depth interviews are of two kinds: one more general and one more focused on texts and documents that shaped that phase. I used a kind of discursive interview with a dialogical style (La Mendola 2009; Ghilardi & La Mendola 2021) to which I was trained in the past for other research studies.

Then, the research involves professionals from the judiciary field and from the social services asking them – through a particular kind of in-depth interview, the interview to the double – for explaining how they read and interpret the legal texts translating them in a language that fits the needs of the mothers who are their clients. The interview to the double was originally conceived as a way of capturing and documenting practical knowledge (Oddone, Re e Briante 1977; Gherardi 1990; Nicolini 2009). Therefore, it focuses on the interviewee's practices, so that the interviewer can collect the moral and normative dimensions of these practices. During the interviewee act as an instructor for the researcher who will act as the interviewee's double.

Then, the study involves the mothers interviewed in a photo-voice activity (Tartari 2021) asking for collecting pictures that they consider significant about that phase of transition and for drawing a map of the journey they did through institutions and practitioners (professionals) during their separation/divorce and after that.

In a subsequent phase of the research process, materials collected in the photo-voice activities are discussed in small focus groups of participants or with individual meetings when participants do not like sharing their identities and thoughts with other participants, thus involving, in separate meetings, both the mothers and professionals who were interviewed.

The main goal of the project is to sensitize policymakers and stakeholders about the disjunctures that single mothers experience in this specific phase and about how institutional discourses and practices shape their future trajectories (and, indirectly, the trajectories of their children). Therefore, participants were informed through an information sheet and a consent form about the final activities, which have the aim to reach out to these specific non-academic audiences.

Discussion. *Interrogating the selves: from self-criticism to reflexivity.*

The aim of this discussion is two-fold: 1) to point out the methodology I used to develop reflexivity and responsible practices for social change during the research process concerning: the researcher, the women, and the professionals involved as participants; 2) to give particular visibility to the process of interrogating the researcher's self/selves in the different research phases.

1 – The researcher's multiple selves

I will begin from the interrogation of the researcher's self, outlining the main aspects that characterize my Self as a researcher and as a woman and how I critically analyzed them to develop reflexivity. I was aware that my standpoint must not interfere with the mothers' standpoint.

Therefore, I began exploring my vulnerabilities to make it clear the relationships with the vulnerabilities of the participants, in particular single mothers. This is one of my accounts during the fieldwork.

I am dealing with feelings of being on the margins. I am white, middle-class, educated much more than my interviewees, middle-aged, I come from a country that is not always well-represented in the public discourse in the UK or Belgium. In the past, I belonged to the judicial elites of a western country as I acted as a court-appointed expert. However, during the research, I belong to neither a judicial elite nor a local cultural elite (when I conduct research outside Italy). Yet, now I am a fixed-term (precarious) academic researcher in international mobility with a study funded by a supranational institutional body.

How does my positionality (as a researcher, professional, woman, single mother of a young child, middle-aged, middle-class, white, well-educated, immigrant, non-native, fixed-term,...) reflect my agenda in this research project? So how are these differences, these vulnerabilities of mine affecting my ability to listen to these women? How can I bridge these cultural and social divides? Who can help me in improving my position? What assumptions am I making concerning gender and parenting? What assumptions am I making concerning how institutions rule mothering practices and motherhood after divorce? How can I ask questions that generate reflexivity without influencing them (their self, experience, accounts)?

These questions and reflections helped me in analyzing my positions and participants' positions in the research process. From the chaos of spontaneous and troubling questions, I began organizing my thoughts and understanding my positions.

First, as I have multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary experience *as a professional and as an academic researcher*, therefore I am both an insider and an outsider of at least two different disciplines (psychology and sociology), two different professional fields as a psychologist and as a sociologist, inside and outside at least two different organizational systems (academia, private sector, public health system, national justice system).

My background as a psychologist and psychotherapist helps me in a self-critical action about how I interact with other people, the words I use (e.g., the lexicon, the sentence structures, the linguistic codes), how I look at people, how I behave in specific situations. As my first training is as a psychologist, one of my cultural selves in interaction with others is very imbued of psychological

notions and meanings. However, even if I use these aspects to understand how to accommodate, to adjust my interactions with other people, this cultural self is less present or sometimes absent when I come to listen to interviewees' accounts, to analyze and interpret them. This is one of the reasons I chose to develop my career in the field of sociology: I find myself completely uncomfortable in assessing other people through diagnostic categories from the mental health field. The reason is that I do not agree with taking for granted the power of some predominant ideas or groups, which aim to objectify others and maintain a position of power.

However, I should add that I worked for almost 20 years as a court-appointed expert and private appointed expert in the field of parental responsibilities evaluation, in particular for children custody, and I always felt the power imbalance between different professionals' roles and between professionals and parents in the process of evaluation. I always noticed how ideological codes ruled the decisions I took and the assessment I wrote for the courts and how much difficult was acting at the border of those ideological codes in some cases.

It is starting from this discomfort of noticing this power imbalance that during the interviews I sometimes feel the need to make it clear about my past activities as a court-appointed / private appointed expert and my feelings in those professional situations. First, I clarified to myself my discomfort in evaluating people within a specific ideological code and through judicial practices and procedures that do not always consider people's needs and not always consider social or cultural dimensions, but often only the psychological dimension. If I decided to share this experience from my professional life it was to not deceive the trust of the interviewees (who might have discovered my identity later), and also to stimulate, during the interview, a more detailed analysis about that specific situation of evaluation for the court. When I shared this experience, I did it only with other professionals like lawyers, psychologists, and social workers and never with the mothers. Sharing this information worked and the interviewee shared with me not only his/her frustration toward the court-appointed expert or the private-appointed expert, but also more detailed and genuine information about the practices that s/he considered not suitable in properly evaluating her/his case.

I chose very simple sentences to express my critical perspective toward my professional experience:

“Before my career as a researcher, as a sociologist, I worked for several years as a forensic psychologist, as a court-appointed expert and private appointed expert in the field of parental responsibilities evaluation. Now I look at that experience in a self-critical way, sometimes I look at the parents I met in those years and their difficulties through the process of evaluation and this is one of the reasons, which gave me an impulse to start this research project. I know that other professionals cannot share my view, but we can discuss it”.

Then, my self-critical act concerns my position *as a woman*: white, middle-class, middle-aged, educated woman, from a rural northern area of Italy, who has experience as a single mother and experience of social mobility from a low-class to a middle-class position. However, when I moved for my fellowship to Belgium in 2019 I added the status and experience of an immigrant to myself, and when I moved for the field trips to the different sites of my research, I added several different experiences of cultural breaks. When I come to speak and interact with my participants, my original cultural self is still present with its prejudices and preconceptions, which I try to counter thanks to the dialogical training I followed in different periods of my life.

These different selves and locations could not be disregarded and I decided to unveil them with very simple sentences, which highlighted core issues, like for instance: *I am a single mother too, but I have never gone through the process of separation or divorce. So, I share some differences and similarities with the mothers like you who participate in this research project, and I am here to understand better your experience that, like mine, can be different from those of others and might help in improving the situation for other single mothers in the future.*

In both these situations, with the mothers and the professionals, unveiling part of my experience and self had the aim to reduce the imbalance of power and to stimulate a more equal discussion. I never did this at the beginning of the interview, but later when the process of knowledge exchange was already started and I felt that the moment required a clarification.

At the beginning of the interview, instead, I chose to not categorize myself and my position(s) and to make it explicit in this early phase of contact. Following the suggestions from Howard Becker (...), I preferred speaking of what I was doing and not of who I was (e.g., Not “I am the researcher in charge of”, but “I am conducting this study on...”). Even if some of these positions were visible (e.g., my age), other positions were momentarily kept as implicit or suspended.

Unveiling part of my experience and self didn't work in some of the interviews where the interviewees arrived with many preconceptions against researchers and research and they tried to avoid being involved in the discussion and exposing their selves, and stayed in a very defensive position.

Finally, I would add that being an experienced professional is not always an advantage when you are trying to conduct research in a field very close to your professional field. As a court-appointed expert, I am an experienced professional in “languages and behavioral grammars” which allows facing a judicial process such as a divorce or separation in which the interviewees were involved. This closeness and experience expose me to the risk of *institutional captures*, which Dorothy Smith (2005, 225) defines as those situations in which “both informants and researcher are familiar with institutional discourse, know how to speak it, and hence can lose touch with the informant's experientially based knowledge.” To not “lose touch” I had continuously to pay attention to the language they and I use and to the abstract map of their actual journey through the judicial process. To not lose touch I asked them what I was taking for granted about that process and their experience, by asking them which parts of their experience my interview had not covered. However, the risk of losing touch does not concern only the situation of the interview, but it increases during the process of data interpretation when in our loneliness as researchers we interpret data without involving the participants. This is exactly the reason why I decided to prolong the study by adding a second interview, the photo-voice activities, and the focus groups, to preserve the freshness of the participant's experientially based knowledge and reflexivity.

I chose to start the fieldwork from Italy because in my context of origin, speaking my language, it would have been easier for me to notice some dynamics related to my acceptance in the field, to participants' resistances toward the research, and to "tune" my Self and positions with their selves and positions. It was useful, as I felt much more confident in the research process I was conducting.

Mothers' selves and reflexivity

One of my main questions in preparing the interview guide concerned how to stimulate reflexivity, in each different category of participants, from their position.

In the field sites (in particular in the UK), I met mothers with many misconceptions about research and the role of researchers. Single mothers are often researched as a deviant category, therefore they try to avoid researchers or to use some forms of social camouflage. In addition, I was a cultural outsider, non-native, non-mother-tongue, and immigrant.

Therefore, the first choice I made to access participants was to identify research assistants who belonged to the same cultures or who shared similar positions with the interviewees intending to reduce the power imbalance and facilitate the process of recruitment, the interactions during the interview, and to stimulate reflexive accounts. When participants did not speak English or Italian, I conducted the interviews with the help of these assistants. In Belgium, in particular, I chose two assistants who belong to different ethnical groups in order to reduce the power imbalance between the interviewees and us. This strategy was fruitful in many situations, even if interviewing with the presence of an assistant/translator/cultural mediator is not always an easy task, prolongs the interview time, and presents some risks. I trained the assistants with the aim to prevent the more common mistakes that concern the power imbalance during the interviews. Anyway, the individualities of the assistants, their positions, their selves played a visible role during the interactions with the interviewees. I wrote down this note during one of the first stages of interviewing in Belgium.

One of the assistants (she is white and native) is a cultural insider with regard to the white Flemish mothers. She shows a minor sensitiveness during the interactions with the interviewees, about how to build a dialogical interaction, about how to understand and interpret the dynamics that concern differences about class and intersections. She uses abstract and stereotyped categories which come from her education (in social work) but without self-criticism or considering actual life. She shows some naïve knowledge of her cultural and social context. She often is passive during the interviews and loses attention as she takes for granted some contents.

One of the other assistants (she is black and non-native but immigrated here during primary school age, from a low-class family) has a marked intercultural sensitiveness in interactions. I think, in her everyday life she has to face the consequences of being black and non-native even if she speaks fluently the local language. She has direct experience of the meaning of living with differences and intersections and shows to understand that the mothers have a load of differences and intersections as well. She always follows actively the conversation and interactions with the interviewee and does everything possible to ensure that I would be able to understand what people are saying.

During the conduction of the interviews, that intercultural sensitiveness played a positive role in correcting or balancing many of the biases, which we are bringing into that interactive situation.

With the first interview, I try to train the interviewees to some reflexive practices from the start. In other words, the interview started with an introduction that frames the core meaning of my act: “I am here to listen to you without prejudice; your experience is very valuable for me and the research project”.

The following text concerns the introduction to the interview that I proposed to the women involved in my project:

With this interview, I would like that you tell me about your experience as a single parent and the phase of transition from double parenthood to single motherhood when you met the judicial or legal system. As I ask you to tell me about your experience, there are no correct or incorrect answers, but only your experience is important. For this reason, for example, I will not provide you with a list of answers to choose from like in other kinds of interviews; I am here to listen to you and your experiences, as you will guide me through

different moments of your life. There will be times where I will ask you to elaborate on certain topics, so that we can discover the profound aspects of the topic, instead of talking about what usually happens. Therefore, the details of your experience are important. Everything we tell each other will be kept between us, to preserve your privacy.

(Note: If the translator is present, the researcher says 'also [name] will respect the same agreement').

Do you agree with this? Thank you. Now we can start...

[First Question] Part of what I am interested in studying is the period in which you got in touch with the judicial system. Please, could you tell me, from the beginning, your experience with the judicial system during the phase of transition from double to single parenthood, from the time you were two parents together and the moment you become a single mother?

This starting is also called “communicative agreement” (La Mendola 2009) and it has the explicit aim to reduce the power imbalance and to give room and time to reflection and self-reflection. La Mendola (2009) developed his approach following the ideas of Michail Bakhtin (1981) on dialogical interactions. He utilizes the metaphor “tuning a musical instrument” when he describes the work of the researcher’s and interviewee’s selves in “tuning” each other about the aims, the conduction, the time, the interactions in carrying out the interview. The researcher’s and interviewee’s selves contribute in co-carrying out the process of the interview with the aim of generating reflexivity. When necessary, parts of this communicative agreement can be mentioned again during the interview. Like in other research projects, also in this project, even if the challenge of many different positions was present, this agreement/tuning worked in generating reflexivity. Interviewees who do not rush and who listen to their thoughts and discuss their different positions are proof that the “tuning” was done and worked.

The most difficult interviews concerned interviewees with a greater power imbalance, in particular the first generation of immigrants from some north African countries with whom the interviews were conducted in an office of the social services in a period in which Covid-19 preventive measures were still running. Even if the social service had these contacts because they were

involved in a group for women empowerment running at the same social service, sometimes the evaluative framework of the social service did not allow women to tell their experience overtly. The second interview – a kind of interview based on the texts that rule the civil trial for separation/divorce – invited the interviewees to reconstruct in a more detailed way how the texts of their trial affected their experience. This interview was of great importance in reflexively discovering mothers' role in that process. During the interview, some interviewees realized that they had never had a real role in writing the documents directed to the court or in reading them, or they had never read the decisions from the court. Instead, other interviewees realized that their contribution in writing or reviewing those documents was significant and valuable, even if sometimes their lawyers had never recognized their efforts and contribution. Some of the mothers interviewed had never had access or had never read the texts concerning the court's decisions, their attorneys' petitions, even if they concerned them and their children. Often their knowledge of those documents was based on a kind of attorney's reading for them. Sometimes this situation was directly related to the low education of the informants and it shows much about the vulnerability of some participants who tried to hide that they had never had these documents at their disposal. After these interviews, the photo-voice activities and the focus groups had the aim to generate reflexivity in a research process that lasted many months. However, some immigrant women recruited by the social service declined the invitation to participate in these activities. Otherwise, other immigrant women who were not involved with the social service accepted the invitation. It was exactly during the interviews conducted at the social service that I had fewer opportunities to share information about my positionality, my Self as a researcher and as a woman due to different reasons: the institutional framework of the social service, the timing (to respect the timing for using their room at the service); the presence of the assistant with fewer abilities concerning intercultural communication; a social context (that of the social service) that stigmatizes the passage of personal information from the professional to the informants/clients; the door opened to circulate air during

the interview (due to the Covid-19 regulations) and that did not ensure the respect for the privacy.

This puzzling situation represents very well how our intentions can meet obstacles:

Another frequent and dangerous situation was caused by the *institutional captures* (Smith 2005):

both the participants and I were captured by the institutional discourse concerning the law on children's custody. Too much of that law was taken for granted and too little was discussed critically.

I would share here the case of Samira, a young divorced mother, who immigrated to Belgium from a North Africa country when she was at primary school, married and divorced (with a very conflictual divorce) from a man from North Africa who she met in Belgium. Samira was self-critical about her positions (culture, class, gender, intersections), tried to resist institutional captures (e.g., the ideological discourse on shared parenting), and countered some decisions taken by the attorney in her place. I conducted two very long interviews with her, in which she shared insightful comments on her personal and judicial situation and, in general on the single mothers' condition.

At my final question, "Just to make sure we covered everything; is there anything you want to add on the things I asked or I didn't ask?" she replied:

Single mothers need models, positive inspirations... to fight the stigma around them. Empowering mums is very important, explaining to them that they can do it all by themselves, alone. The "Disney culture" teaches them they have to be married and be in a couple for raising children. But society can support them and they can do it alone. I have a stipend and it is enough for my children and me. [...] It is our culture that represents mothers in this way, but also men and women. [...] My mother was very sweet... the rainbow... Disney world!... and he [my brother] was very naive. There are many men in the same situation. I see this also in the students that I have, they are very naive. This is the impact of the Disney world. [...]

Our culture, but not only the Moroccan culture but also the Western countries culture... It is not true that you as a single mother will stay alone for the rest of your life! I have students who are very worried about losing virginity and it is the same kind of representation: if you lose your virginity after that you will be able to find other men, it is not a problem. And for single mothers, it is the same: if you lose your husband but you

are alone, and you are not a virgin, it is not a problem, you have many other qualities, many other things that you are able to do. Single mothers need positive models. I got these models around me from people outside my family. They thought I would be able to do it by myself, and I did it.

After the interviews, the photo-voice that involves the mothers already interviewed has the aim to discuss work in-depth on their needs and disjunctures and in creating materials, which can reach out to professionals, policymakers, and stakeholders.

Professionals' reflexivity

Before this research project, I conducted other interviews with professionals within the judicial system in my home country. Usually, these interviews were difficult to conduct because this kind of interviewees plays a professional role that, using Erving Goffman's suggestions, requires a high degree of defense of the backstage and to perform a high degree of correspondence between the professional self and the private self. I knew that trying to ask for telling significant episodes during the interview to collect their experience and generate reflexivity did not always work. This was the reason why I decided to use the interview to the double (ITTD).

The ITTD is an interviewing technique created by some Italian occupational psychologists who conducted research studies in Italian factories in the Seventies. The ITTD was elaborated to recover and legitimize the local knowledge that workers learned on the job and passed on to novices (Nicolini 2009) and it has its roots in the Marxist tradition. Researchers in the Seventies reported that this interview technique helped to uncover some of the more hidden aspects of the local practices that the older workers transmit to the novice workers. This technique made the workers aware of new possibilities of action. After the Seventies, other French and Italian scholars (Gherardi 1990; Oddone & Briante 1977) developed and applied this kind of interview in research studies in the field of organizational studies, sociology of work, and ergonomics.

In my research study, the interview to the double (ITTD) was adapted to a context different from the original one and it posed the challenge to stimulate reflexivity in a category of interviewees usually difficult to involve in research: lawyers and other professionals involved in the judicial evaluation of parents for children custody. In this research, the ITTD shows its great potential in generating reflexivity. Even if the start of the interview is not easy and requires to explain in detail how the interview works, during the interview the process of imagining me as their double produced some hilarious and ironic statements and thoughts that contributed to improve the trust relationship and to reduce the power imbalance between the interviewee and the researcher. The process of looking at themselves and their work from a different perspective worked by stimulating a reflexive rethinking about actions and practices. Even if sometimes interviewees lost the thread and used generalization and typification of the situations if invited in focusing continuously on the task of “giving instructions” to me, they were able to go beyond an initial suspicion about revealing professional practices and strategies. The task of “giving instructions” requires going back and forth through the past experiences, the clients’ characteristics, requests and expectations, the written rules, the other professionals’ or colleagues’ expectations, the interviewee’s self, and the researcher’s request. Therefore, this task requires keeping in mind the others’ point of views and positions, and later this process helps in producing reflexive accounts about what helps single mothers and what does not help them at all during the trial and after. If the interviewer does not listen to the list of instructions in a merely passive way, but if s/he interacts with the interviewee asking for explanations about how those particular instructions work in particular situations, the possibilities of collecting reflexive accounts are greater. In other words, the questions with Garfinkel’s style may facilitate the generation of reflexive accounts.

These are, briefly, the potentialities of the ITTD, a technique too disregarded in qualitative research and that can be fruitfully utilized in Institutional Ethnography if, in the process of “asking and giving instructions” from the side of the interviewer and of the interviewee, the researcher does not disregard the role of the texts.

The following text concerns the initial explanations I provided to the interviewee.

With this interview, I will ask you for telling me your experience as a lawyer with trials for children's custody evaluation. I will ask you for imagining me as your 'double' and to give me all useful suggestions to be substituted in your job and your daily work by me without being discovered by your colleagues.

You will conduct me in different moments of your professional life; if sometimes it will be necessary, I only will try to suggest to you some aspects on which you can focus your attention. How much more you will describe specific situations much more you will help me. Therefore, the details of your experience are important.

All we will tell each other will be kept between me and you, to preserve your privacy.

Are you agree with this? Thank you. Now we can start...

[First Question] Could you give me instructions about how I should behave in a trial where a mother asks for sole custody of children and the father does not agree with this solution? Please, could you start from the preparation of the petition or other documents, the hearings, until the final decision and after...

After the interviews, the focus group organized with professionals has the aim to discuss fragments from the interviews with the mothers and other data from the photo-voice.

Conclusion. Developing reflexivity with responsibility.

My fieldwork experience in this research project shows how much difficult is the task of approaching the research field reflexively and trying to generate reflexivity for and with participants, in particular when the research has multi-site fieldwork in different countries, with different categories of interviewees, interviewees with cultural differences, and potentially vulnerable categories of interviewees. Without these attempts to generate reflexivity, my fieldwork would have been far less meaningful. Furthermore, analyzing positions and how this information can be shared with participants is extremely necessary for the research process. This is what I did during the whole research process.

However, being reflexive implies responsibilities, and soliciting reflexivity implies responsibilities as well. Therefore, developing reflexivity with responsibility is a process that concerns the entire research journey, from the writing of the proposal until the dissemination of the results. Many of these responsibilities should have been known, supported and clarified in advance, from the beginning, as part of the ethical premises of the project. Being responsible implies “abilities”, which implies skills: the ability to respond to others appropriately. However, the term “response” is used here metaphorically and holistically.

I would conclude by offering some reflections and practical considerations about how to practice reflexivity with responsibility.

- Reflexivity is to be considered as a “holistic process that takes place along all stages of the research process” (Hesse Biber & Piatelli 2012).
- Our standpoint should not interfere with the participant's standpoint.
- Our self should be analyzed about our positions and borders (e.g., vulnerabilities, insiderness and outsidersness, backgrounds, ideological codes, cultural self, etc.)
- We should analyze how much we are able to face the “border work” during the research process.
- Sometimes sharing thoughts about our own experience/position can help in exploring participants’ experience and in promoting reflexivity.
- Sometimes it can be fruitful considering and introducing ourselves (researchers) as not a category, but as actions.
- To reduce the power imbalance and improve the contacts with participants when the researcher is not a cultural insider, assistants can help in this process if properly selected and trained (in particular in international projects).
- We can start the fieldwork from anywhere we feel more confident.
- We should pay attention *to not losing touch* with the informant’s experientially based knowledge from the beginning of the research process until data analysis and dissemination.

- We should consider carefully how to write and present the *communicative agreement* at the beginning of the research, interviews, and other research activities to reduce the power imbalance and to give room and time to reflection and self-reflection.
- We should not lose touch with the texts, which organize participants' everyday life in all the research activities.
- We should look for new techniques, which can help in generating reflexivity (ITTD is one of them).
- We can work on our Selves in order to reflect on our positions, intersections, vulnerabilities, similarities, differences, and resistances towards the participants.
- We should use research designs that propose a process of generating reflexivity and that, where this involves working in the direction of social change through outreach activities (which involve non-academic audience), this change can be brought out gradually (so as not to weigh too much on the participants in terms of responsibility).
- We need to question the responsibility of bringing people to the awareness of their relationships, social categories, and intersections. People are not always able to accept these sociological readings of their existence, they are not always able to understand them appropriately (i.e. without causing harm to their Selves), and they are not always able to explain them to the next generation or to omit them if necessary. What will change in their lives after they become aware of sections and intersections?
- We should question ourselves more about our responsibilities in generating social change.
- We always should acknowledge participants for their efforts in participating in our research.
- We should interrogate ourselves about how much the research process has been changing us as researchers and people.

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